

ASSESSMENT OF INVOLVEMENT OF FARM PARENTS IN THEIR SCHOOL GOING CHILDREN'S EDUCATION

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Abstract

A study was conducted in four villages of Parbhani district, Marathwada region of Maharashtra state to examine the assessment of involvement of farm parents in their school going children's education. The data was collected through personal interviews and observations of school going children's parents. This research article examines the involvement of farm parents in their children's learning at home, with a particular focus on their role in assisting with school projects. Through a qualitative approach that includes surveys and personal interviews with farm families, the study explores how farm parents engage in educational activities, the strategies they employ to support their children's learning, and the resources available in farm families. Findings reveal that active involvement of farm mothers in their child's learning at home and in helping their child in completion of school projects was seen as compared to farm fathers except providing materials and supplies needed for completion of school projects which enhances their understanding of academic concepts. Additionally, the research highlights how parents provide hands-on support for completion of school projects, fostering creativity and critical thinking skills. This study underscores the significance of parental involvement in education, especially in rural contexts, and offers insights into how farm families can effectively nurture their children's academic growth at home.

Keywords: Farm mothers, Farm fathers, School going children, Farm parents, Involvement, Education.

Introduction

Parents should participate in the education of their children. In particular, parental involvement in their child's learning process offers many opportunities for success. Parents increase engagement and communication with their children and become more sensitive and responsive to their children's social, emotional and intellectual developmental needs.

Parents can participate in their children's education by showing concern for their children's academic performance and dedicating themselves to their children's education by attending parent-teacher meetings in order to better understand their children's performance. Parents can help their children at home in a number of ways, including reading with them, supervising homework, talking about the school day and events, participation in learning activities and help to prepare for exams. Many parents whose children are currently enrolled in a particular school are extremely concerned, frequently volunteering to help in their child's classroom, staying in constant contact with their child's teachers, helping with their homework, participating in school projects, and talking to teachers about their child's specific academic strengths and weaknesses.

In addition, family involvement in education is said to help children grow to be productive, responsible members of society. That is, if parents participate in educating their children, it is the same as saying that the school is actively implementing change or development among students. As the mother's involvement increased, so did the school teacher and the parent's involvement are increased, teachers and school administrators also raise the chance to realize quality reform in education. As parents become more involved, teachers and school administrators also improve their ability to implement quality reforms in education.

Materials And Methods**Table: Details of sample rural farm parents based on age and gender**

Demographic area of sample farm parents	Details of sample rural farm parents			
	Number	Age (Yrs.)	Gender	
			Farm mothers	Farm fathers
Rural	300	18-45	150	150

Plan of statistical analysis:

Frequency: Frequency was calculated to find out the number of the farm parents involved in their school going children's education and to study the other variables considered for the research.

The present study on, 'Assessment of Involvement of Farm Parents in Their School Going Children's Education' was planned with an objective to study the assessment of involvement of farm parents in their school going children's education and its effects on their scholastic achievements of their children aged 6-10 years. The materials and methods which were adopted for carrying out the research are presented under the following heads,

Locale of the study: Total 4 villages of Parbhani taluka namely Jamb, Kinhol, Pedgaon and Bargaon of Parbhani district of Marathwada region of Maharashtra state were selected.

Selection of the sample parents: Purposive random sampling method was used and 300 samples (150 Farm mothers and 150 Farm fathers) having children in the age range of 6-10 years belonging to different SES groups were chosen.

Employed research tools and techniques:

Structured and open-ended interview schedule cum checklist: A structured and open-ended interview schedule was prepared to elicit information from farm parents of school going children about personal background, parental involvement in their children's education, educational activities performed by school going children. For testing the suitability of research tools, it was pre-tested for its clarity validity and adequacy on 40 samples (20 Farm mothers and 20 Farm fathers) having school going children in age group of 6-10 years age from rural areas who were exclusive of the final sample of 300.

Socio-economic status scale: Kuppuswamy's modified Socio-Economic Status scale 2023 was used to assess the socio-economic status of selected farm parents in rural area.

Methods adopted for data collection: Purposive random sampling method, Personal interview and Participatory observations.

Distribution of sample (n=300)

Z Test: 'Z' test was applied to compare the percentages of the various responses to the different parameters with regard to the involvement of farm mothers and farm fathers in their school going children's education as per the standard procedure given by Sharma, 2005.

Correlation: Correlation coefficient measures the strength of association and its types (+ve /-ve) between independent and dependent variables. Therefore, correlation of coefficient was computed for assessing the relationship between dependent and independent variables I present research study by using formula.

Result and Discussion

The study on “Assessment of Involvement of Farm Parents in Their School Going Children’s Education” was carried out in randomly selected 4 villages of Parbhani district, Marathwada region of Maharashtra state. To carry out this research study, the data was collected on the basis of structured cum open ended interview schedule and also using Kuppuswamy’s socio-economic status scale revised by Sheikh, M.S. (2023). The collected information was pooled, tabulated, analyzed and discussed in this chapter.

- 1) Background information of the sample rural farm parents
- 2) Involvement of farm parents in their child’s learning at home
- 3) Role of farm parents in helping their child in completion of school projects

Background information of the sample rural farm parents

Table 1. reveals about background information of the sample rural farm parents. Irrespective of gender, with regard to their type of family, it was recorded that relatively higher percentages of the farm parents were from nuclear families (62.66%) followed by joint families (32.00%) and extended families (5.33%). Irrespective of gender about 53.33 per cent of the sample farm parents belonged to the small size families followed by the middle size (36.66%) and large size (10.00 %) families.

Table 1. Background information of the sample rural farm parents

Parental Background information	Farm parents (300)	
	Farm mothers (150)	Farm fathers (150)
Age of parents(yrs)		
18-25	72.00 (108)	36.66(55)
26-35	28.00 (42)	46.66(70)
36-45	---	16.66(25)
Family types		
Nuclear	62.66 (94)	62.66 (94)
Joint	32.00 (48)	32.00 (48)
Extended	5.33 (8)	5.33 (8)
Family Sizes		
Small (<4)	53.33 (80)	53.33 (80)
Middle (5-8)	36.66 (55)	36.66 (55)
Large (>5)	10.00 (15)	10.00 (15)
Family annual income		
Below 40,0000	70.00 (105)	33.33(50)
40,000-80,000	28.00 (42)	54.66 (82)
Above 80,000	2.00 (3)	12.00 (18)
Socio-economic Status		
Upper middle	13.33 (20)	13.33 (20)
Lower middle	30.00 (45)	32.00 (48)
Upper lower	35.33 (53)	37.33 (56)
Lower	21.33 (32)	17.33 (26)
Education		
Post graduate	---	4.66 (7)
Graduate	4.66 (7)	24.66 (37)
HSC/Diploma	62.00 (93)	54.00 (81)
SSC	32.00 (48)	16.66 (25)
Primary School	1.33 (2)	---
Occupation		
Agriculture alone	74.00 (111)	76.66 (115)

With respect to the family annual income, it was observed that irrespective of gender relatively a higher percentages of farm parent’s family annual income were below Rs.40,000 (Farm mothers 70.00% and Farm fathers 33.33%) followed by Rs.40,000 to Rs.80,000 (Farm mothers 28.00% – Farm fathers 54.66%) and above Rs. 80,000 (Farm mothers 2.00% – Farm fathers 12.00%). However, about the socioeconomic status of the farm parents about 35.33 per cent of farm mothers and 37.33 per cent farm fathers belonged to upper lower socio-economic status, while 30.00 per cent of farm mothers and 32.00 per cent farm fathers belonged to lower middle socio-economic status followed by lower socio-economic status (Farm mothers 21.33% and Farm fathers 17.33%). However about 13.33 per cent of them observed to be in upper middle socio-economic status.

It is clear from the results that majority of sample farm parents (62.00% of farm mothers and 54.00% of farm fathers) completed HSC / diploma followed by SSC (32.00% of farm mothers and 16.66% of farm fathers), graduates (4.66% of farm mothers and 24.66% of farm fathers). Only 1.33 per cent of farm mothers, completed primary school. Only 4.66 per cent of farm fathers, completed post-graduation. With regard to parental occupation of the children, it was observed that the higher percentages of farm mothers (74.00%) and farm fathers (76.66%) were farmer (agriculture alone) followed by agriculture allied activities (5.33% of farm mothers and 7.33% of farm fathers), agriculture labourer services (18.66% of farm mothers and 11.33% of farm fathers) and agricultural business (2.00% of farm mothers and 4.66% of farm fathers).

Agriculture allied activities (Animal husbandry, Fishery)	5.33 (8)	7.33 (11)
Agriculture+ labourer work	18.66 (28)	11.33 (17)
Agriculture + business	2.00 (3)	4.66 (7)

Figures in parentheses indicate frequencies

Involvement of farm parents in their child's learning at home

Table 2. illustrated about involvement of farm parents in their child's learning at home. More than half of farm mothers (61.33%) and very less farm fathers (28.66%) were reported their participation in learning activities of their child. Near about 40.66 per cent of farm mothers and less percentages (28.00%) of farm fathers were reported that they communicate with their child about different types of activities carried out at school.

It is clearly noted that more than half of the farm mothers (56.00%) were reported that they help their child to prepare for examination as compared to farm fathers (22.00%) whereas more than half of farm

mothers (54.00%) and very less farm fathers (15.33%) were reported that they read text books of their child. Similar trend was found for content discuss of chapters of text books with their child. Highly significant differences were noted between farm mothers and farm fathers in participating learning activities with their child, communication with child about various activities carried out in school, helping child to prepare for examinations, reading text books of child and discussion regarding content of chapters of text books. On the basis of results, it can be suggested that, there is great need of farm parent's involvement in above mentioned activities.

Table 2. Involvement of farm parents in their child's learning at home

Involvement of farm parents in their child's learning at home	Farm parents (300)		Z values
	Farm mothers (150)	Farm fathers (150)	
Participation in learning activities	61.33(92)	28.66(43)	6.09**
Communicate about activities conducted at school	40.66(61)	28.00(42)	2.21*
Help to prepare for exams	56.00(84)	22.00(33)	6.44**
Read text books of child	54.00(81)	15.33(23)	7.79**
Discussion about content of chapters of text books	54.66(82)	12.66(19)	8.64**

Figures in parentheses indicate frequencies *p < 0.05 level **P < 0.01 level

Role of farm parents in helping their child in completion of school projects

Table 3. illustrates about the role of farm parents in helping their child with school projects. Highest percentages of the farm mothers (72.00%) and more than half of farm fathers (53.33%) were reported that they were involved in providing guidance and ideas to child for making school projects followed by less percentages of farm parents (farm mothers 16.00% and farm fathers 11.33%) were involved in assisting with research while making school projects with no any significant difference.

It was observed that less percentages farm mothers (39.33%) and high percentages (82.00%) of farm fathers were involved in helping child with providing materials and supplies. Majority 37.33 per cent of farm mothers and only 16.00 per cent of farm fathers were involved in helping child with proof reading and editing. Similarly, most of the farm mothers (39.33%) were involved in helping their child with supporting time management in making school projects as compared to farm fathers (16.00%). Very highly significant differences were found between providing guidance and ideas, helping with providing materials and supplies, proof reading and editing, supporting time management.

Table 3. Role of farm parents in helping their child in completion of school projects

Role of farm parents in helping their child in completion of school projects	Farm parents (300)		Z values
	Farm mothers (150)	Farm fathers (150)	
Providing guidance and ideas	72.00(108)	53.33(80)	3.46**
Assisting with research	16.00(24)	11.33(17)	1.27 ^{NS}
Helping with providing materials and supplies	39.33(59)	82.00(123)	8.48**
Proofreading and editing	37.33(56)	16.00(24)	4.24**
Supporting time management	39.33(59)	16.00(24)	4.61**

Figures in parentheses indicate frequencies **P < 0.01 level NS – Non-Significant

Summary and Conclusion

In summary, the study highlights the crucial role that farm parents play in their children's education, particularly in the context of home learning and project completion. Regardless of gender, the majority of farm parents were from nuclear families and had small family sizes. The research indicates that this involvement of farm parents not only enhances children's understanding of various subjects but also fosters essential skills such as creativity and problem solving.

In conclusion, the highly significant involvement of farm mothers was found in their children's education than farm fathers so farm father's involvement must be increased for their children's overall academic improvement. The involvement of farm parents in their children's learning is important for fostering academic success and personal growth. By being involved, farm parents not only help their children succeed academically but also strengthen family bonds and encourage a love for learning. Supporting farm families in their educational efforts can lead to better outcomes for children in rural area.

Furthermore, the co-operative nature of working on school projects help to improve communication and teamwork within families, enhancing relationships. Highly significant differences were found between farm parents regarding child's learning at home and in helping children to complete their school project.

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